

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: BALGOBIN****FIRST NAME: ROLPH****PROGRAM CODE: DRCTH****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA**

The author applied UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics
The author did use Zotero to insert references
The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)
My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 0%
The author used the following software: MSWord 2024 on Apple Mac OS

KEY CONCEPTS

1. Rules, and rules of thumb (Cleenwerck 2021; EUCLID 2024, 6-12)
2. American versus British English (EUCLID 2024, 24-33)
3. Style guides
4. The course management system crib sheet (EUCLID 2024, 43-58)
5. Latin abbreviations (EUCLID 2024, 58-64)

EUCLID PAPER FUNDAMENTALS

1) INTRODUCTION

As a new EUCLID doctoral student of Catholic Theology, I am required to take the academic course ACA-401D. This course focuses on international academic writing with a particular focus on doctoral-level work. Given the levels of rigour to be expected of such a programme, I am pleased to engage in this first course and to deal upfront with the challenges of academic writing. This will lay the groundwork for positive progress and save much frustration later.

In this short response paper, I will reflect on five key concepts from the course pack (EUCLID 2024) as well as the tutorial video Basic ACA-401 Tutorial (Cleenwerk 2021). I have interacted in detail with several more critical concepts to prepare this submission as a part of my onboarding for the course and programme. Getting the EUCLID platform basics understood and adequately set up was challenging, and understanding precisely what was expected of me took some time. This was due to the multiple sources of information which, as a new student, had to be studied. The time spent here was fruitful and well-spent, and I am confident it will bear great benefits later.

Concerning this first response paper, I am excited to proceed. Notwithstanding the initial confusion, the material covered is very valuable for this part of the doctoral journey,

and I am excited to learn again at such a high level. In this paper, I will respond to critical concepts concerning rules and rules of thumb, US versus UK English, style guides, crib sheets and Latin abbreviations. I chose some of these because of my lack of familiarity with them rather than their objective importance, hence my exclusion of plagiarism, which is a concept I am already very familiar with and am in complete agreement with the Euclid approach detailed in the course pack (EUCLID 2024, 33).

2) RULES AND RULES OF THUMB

The first chapter helpfully begins by clearly articulating the focus on academic writing. To do this, it emphasises some crucial distinctions from other types of writing. From the paper, I conclude that academic writing is factual rather than creative, tries to answer clear research questions, may target a narrower audience, is generally located within and acknowledges a prior body of work, and seeks to add to this by evidence-based contributions to knowledge. An academic paper also includes citations and references to other related works from which concepts, constructs, or conclusions are relied upon to bolster the validity and reliability of the paper. This distinguishes academic work from other types of writing, such as fiction, opinion pieces, and journalistic articles.

Since academic writing is so specific and different from other writing types, it is crucial to understand the steps for writing a good essay. Concerning my journey, I note with humorous embarrassment the caution against delays in starting (EUCLID, 2024, 7). Otherwise, I find the ideas on starting an academic essay consistent with the distinctions of academic writing. Defining research questions, identifying the literature, data sources, how analysis would be undertaken and ways that conclusions might be presented are all essential elements of planning a paper.

The recommended introduction, body and conclusion format neatly encapsulate the necessary steps for academic paper writing. The eleven-point hierarchy in Figure 1 (EUCLID, 2024, 8) is very instructive, and the self-imposed delay after completion of the draft stage in stage seven is very valuable to me. I have always made extensive revisions when I allow the paper to marinate.

I find referencing very important since it locates the paper within a stream of literature, provides context for the work and refers the reader to related material. EUCLID recommends the Turabian rule of style for in-text referencing, which I find easy to understand and use (EUCLID 2024, 2).

I believe that the rules of thumb for writing a paper provide some practical advice that will yield stronger submissions (EUCLID 2024, 13). I have used this advice in this initial effort, which helped my understanding significantly. Grasping the thesis of my paper, staying focused, trying not to include too much, avoiding generalities and trying to stay interesting are points of advice I agree with. They are particularly helpful for me in this new academic endeavour. Reading the paper aloud and, arguing with myself, presenting questions and counterpoints to my own statements are very useful in developing my thinking, writing and arguments (EUCLID 2024, 14).

3) AMERICAN AGAINST BRITISH ENGLISH

American English has risen in influence since the conclusion of the Second World War. This growth is correlated to the rise of U.S. economic power and its growing influences on technology, culture and entertainment (EUCLID 2024, 25). While I have been aware of the differences between US and British English for some time, this paper provided the opportunity to examine some of these in greater detail. It also gives me a brief opportunity to reflect on how this came to be.

I come from Trinidad and Tobago, a former British colony in close geographic proximity to and in the economic orbit of the USA. We are, therefore, historically and culturally heavily exposed to both uses of English. It helps to note the many examples of pronunciations, spelling and meanings attached to many words. The slight but significant differences in honorifics, grammar and syntax suggest almost infinite ways to offend someone important. Colons and commas are of particular note, as are the plurality of large collective nouns in British English, which I find surprising because of their dissimilarity from what I would generally encounter (EUCLID 2024, 26).

Upon reflection, I have used both styles interchangeably, depending on where I am and the standard terms employed there. This is especially key with words with differences in style, connotation and frequency where the use of terms is primarily more local but very entrenched to the point that using the wrong term would render one unintelligible. Some excellent examples of these are identified in the ACA-401 Coursepack (EUCLID 2024, 28). I have understood from studying the course pack that this is unacceptable, and I have chosen British English and set my Word and Grammarly settings accordingly.

4) STYLE GUIDES

From my study of the material, I understand a style guide to be a particular format for aspects of writing such that what is written is consistent. I find this is important both for the writer and the reader to avoid misunderstanding and ensure coherence. For academic writing, this need for consistency is of manifest import since this ensures a manageable form across publications, authors and even time itself. While I understand there is no set style for any particular type of writing, it is clear to me that establishing one within a set context, in an institution such as EUCLID or the BBC, for example, is essential (EUCLID 2024, 42).

I am therefore grateful that EUCLID has taken the time to establish essential elements of its style and to deploy this using several means at its disposal. Three examples bear this out. The assignment itself is restricted to three to five pages. I am required to use the Turabian rules from the Chicago Manual of Style (Turabian et al. 2018). I believe that it is simple and will greatly benefit me to have had this defined so early in my doctoral journey. Third, the response paper template is of tremendous assistance with the styles already input into Word. I have already found this saves time in editing and improves the final product.

5) THE CMS CRIB SHEET

In the previous section, I reflected on aspects of writing styles that are helpful in academic papers and EUCLID essays. In the course pack, these considerations are greatly expanded in Chapter 6 (EUCLID 2024). I spent considerable time absorbing and reflecting on this material. My reason for doing so is that I recognised that this section had the potential to assist me in avoiding small errors which could delay my progress in the future.

I learned that the Turabian style is really the Chicago Manual of Style for research papers and that both have been published by the University of Chicago Press (EUCLID 2024, 44). This was useful to me since there are so many styles from which to choose, and locating one style within the other was helpful and decluttered my thinking on styles. I feel this was important because I have seen people attempt to switch styles, which has led to great confusion, and I wish to avoid that eventuality.

I was pleased to settle for the purposes of writing for EUCLID in the manner of writing numbers, whether spelling them out or using numbers or Roman numerals. I was unaware of the Chicago Manual of Style rule indicating that numbers should be spelt out from one through one hundred (EUCLID 2024, 47). Presumably, it is ok to use numerals after that, and though I do not expect to find out, I know where to look if I need to.

Finally, the Chicago Manual of Style appears to offer little guidance for academic papers, so the work of Kate Turabian has been invaluable in this regard (Turabian et al. 2018). Turabian guidelines on margins, paper size, indents, fonts, paper weight, justification, spacing and much more have all been operationalised in the template provided to us (EUCLID 2024, 41). This reduces the overhead of setting this up in Word and is of great benefit, I believe, to all students and certainly to me.

6) LATIN ABBREVIATIONS

In undertaking this paper, my preparation involved a deep dive into the various aspects presented by the course pack (EUCLID 2024) and course video tutorial (Cleenwerk 2021). I also spent time with the student orientation documents, which were very detailed. Although this meant a delayed start, I am happy to have taken the time to explore in this response paper aspects of academic writing information that I might ordinarily set aside. This was certainly the case for Latin abbreviations.

Latin abbreviations are an area of great interest to me. This is because I understand them so little, yet I encounter them a lot. I found that much complexity could be avoided by using the English equivalent of Latin abbreviations for EUCLID. Hence, for example, in my heading three, comparing American to British English, I was able to substitute 'against' for 'vs.' as per the guidance of the course pack (EUCLID 2024, 61).

Another learning for me related to the Latin expressions for terms related to those I was familiar with and some related ones I had never encountered before. I always

understood ‘a priori’ as a reference to deductive logic, from causes to effects. I never knew of the expression ‘a posteriori’, referring to effects to causes, that is, inductive reasoning. Similarly, I had never known of the expression ‘a fortiori’ and had never seen it used before (EUCLID 2024, 62). I found these fascinating and a useful expansion to my vocabulary.

Perhaps the most valuable insight for me in considering Latin expressions is how much of what I know as English is contested or, in some cases, not English at all. I was, therefore, glad, in considering this section of the course pack, that EUCLID would have taken the time to make all this plain to me to get me on track faster.

7) **CONCLUSION**

As a first step towards my second doctorate, I feel very fortunate in the way this course is structured. After much prevarication, I am convinced that I have chosen the right place to do this doctoral work. The course pack and video were well designed and challenging to get through, compounded by the many other materials we had to make sense of and my own efforts at recovery from a stroke I suffered two years ago. I am grateful to be here and to learn so much already.

This study period shows me how much I had taken for granted in the use of English and getting familiar with the various aspects that Euclid expects is helpful. I believe that I will successfully traverse the other response papers on the way to the quiz and major paper for successful completion of what already promises to be an excellent course, ACA-401D!

REFERENCES

Cleenwerk, Laurent, dir. 2021. *Basic ACA-401D Tutorial*.
<https://eucliduniversity.net/periods/aca-401d-period-1/>.

Laurent Cleenewerck, and Kabiru Gulma. 2024. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Fifth Edition. Washington DC: Euclid University Press.

Turabian, Kate L., Wayne C. Booth, Gregory G. Colomb, Joseph M. Williams, Joseph Bizup, and William T. FitzGerald. 2018. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*. Ninth edition. Chicago Guides to Writing, Editing, and Publishing. Chicago; London: The University of Chicago Press.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.